

REPORT

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Bibliometric Analysis of Research on Mental Health in the Workplace in Canada, 1991-2002

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Study Highlights

- This study uses the Medline biomedical papers database to measure scientific production on mental health in the workplace (MHWP) during the 1991-2002 period at the world, Canadian, provincial, urban, institutional and researcher levels.
- Although mental illness in the workplace is very costly in economic terms, research on the field is still marginal at the world and Canadian levels – only 0.2 % of biomedical papers address the issue.
- Despite this low level of scientific output, output has nonetheless doubled and tripled during the last twelve years at the world and Canadian levels respectively.
- At the provincial level, Ontario, Quebec, British Columbia and Alberta are leading in terms of the absolute number of papers. Ontario is the clearest leader, however, since it has both a large output and a high production per capita in the field. It also specializes in it.
- Although not leading in absolute terms, Nova Scotia and Manitoba are important players considering their size.
- Toronto and Montreal are the largest producers of papers on MHWP at the urban level.
- The most important institutions in terms of papers on MHWP are McMaster University, Université de Montréal, University of Toronto, University of British Columbia and University of Western Ontario.
- McMaster University, Université Laval and York University are the universities with the largest number of active researchers in MHWP.

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Methods

Working in collaboration with experts appointed by the Institute of Neurosciences, Mental Health and Addiction (INMHA) and the Institute of Population and Public Health (IPPH) of the Canadian Institutes for Health Research (CIHR), the OST/Science-Metrix team defined a controlled vocabulary that precisely defined the field of research on mental health in the workplace. This was validated by looking at the percentage of papers from specialist journals that were selected with these keywords. With these keywords, the OST/Science-Metrix team computed statistics from the Medline database, which is produced by the US National Library of Medicine.

This database has been conditioned by Science-Metrix with a view to producing statistics on scientific publications in the biomedical and clinical medicine sector. The construction of the dataset for the scientometric analysis is essentially based on the use of Medical Subject Headings (MeSH) Terms. These constitute a controlled vocabulary used for indexing papers in Medline. This study uses the conjugation of MeSH terms that represent the field of mental health (e.g. "Stress, Psychological") and of MeSH terms associated with the workplace (e.g. "Occupational Diseases") to identify the papers of which a Canadian is first author.

One caveat associated with the use of this database is that only the address of a paper's first author is compiled. This means that the number of Canadian papers obtained here are minimum figures since they do not consider the effect of co-authorship. In addition, because Medline covers the field of biomedical research and clinical medicine, it is possible that some papers from the social science and the humanities are missing. However, the overall comparative and relative statistics should not be affected. Furthermore, the purpose of this study being the mapping of the distribution of Canadian expertise rather than the identification of every researcher, this limitation is not a handicap.

The data collected were used to produce detailed statistics based on the following indicators:

Number of papers - Number of scientific papers written by authors located in a given geographical, geopolitical or organizational entity (e.g. countries, cities or institutions).

Number of papers per capita – This is a relative measure that accounts for the size of the geographic entities being considered.

Index of specialization - This is an indicator of the intensity of research in a given geographic or organizational entity relative to the overall output for a given reference. For example, if the percentage of Ontario's papers (the geographic entity) in the field of mental health and workplace research is greater than the percentage of papers in this field at the Canadian level (the reference), then Ontario is said to be specializing in this field.

For the purpose of the report, relevant indicators have been used for data aggregated by province, by city, by most active institution and by leading researcher.

1. Introduction

This report examines the scientific production of Canadian researchers in the field of mental health in the workplace (MHWP) using scientometric methods and the Medline database. The output of the last twelve years (1991-2002) is studied in Section 1, and in Section 2, Canada's output is compared to that of the world. We will see that Canada has a slightly greater percentage of its papers in the area of mental health in the workplace than the world average.

Section 3 examines the scientific output of the Canadian provinces. Not surprisingly, Ontario is a clear leader, and Quebec is second followed by British Columbia and Alberta. Although the aforementioned provinces lead in absolute terms, Nova Scotia and Manitoba are important in relative terms (papers per capita; specialization index). Section 4 looks at mental health in the workplace research at the urban and institutional levels, while Section 5 provides a list of the most active researchers in the field.

2. Scientific output at the world level

Figure 1 reveals that the percentage of papers on MHWP grows faster in Canada than at the world level. In fact, the proportion of papers on MHWP is nearly 50% greater in Canada than at the world level – more than 0.3% in Canada vs. more than 0.2% at the world level. Although the proportion of Canadian papers on MHWP dropped markedly in 1995 and 1996, there is a clear tendency of more Canadian papers in the biomedical sector being written in MHWP. In fact, the proportion of papers written in this field grew in eight of the twelve years studied. One must note that the yearly variations observed here are not exceptional for a small scientific field, and the field will no doubt show more stability if growth continues.

Figure 1. Share of papers on MHWP in Canada and in the world per year, 1991-2002
 Source: Compiled by Science-Metrix from the Medline database.

Figure 2 reveals that between 1991 and 2002 papers in MHWP increased by 75% in absolute terms at the world level, that is, from 535 papers in 1990 to 940 papers in 2002. In Canada, growth was even more important, with production more than trebling from 14 papers in 1991 to 52 in 2002. The share of the total MHWP papers written by Canada more than doubled from 2.6% in 1991 to 5.5% in 2002. On average, Canada was responsible for 4.4% of papers on MHWP, and it authored 3.7% of papers in the biomedical field indexed in Medline. This means that Canada specializes in MHWP (Specialization Index of 1.2). By comparison, Canada produces about 4% of the world scientific literature in natural and engineering sciences.

Although total output is small when considered in relation to the economic costs associated with mental illness in the workplace, the field is clearly rising rapidly at the international level and is growing faster still in Canada.

Figure 2. Papers on MHWP in Canada and in the world per year, 1991-2002
 Source: Compiled by Science-Metrix from the Medline database.

3. Scientific output at the provincial level

Within Canada, Ontario has a clear lead over the other provinces in the field of MHWP. The proportion of Canadian output is more than double that of its closest competitor, that is, Quebec (46% of Canadian papers are authored in Ontario versus 21% in Quebec). British Columbia and Alberta are on a par, each with 9% of the Canadian output. Manitoba and Saskatchewan together account for 8% of the papers, whereas the Atlantic Provinces account for 7%. This distribution is similar to that obtained for all scientific disciplines. For instance, Ontario published 45% of the papers in the Science Citation Index in 2000, Quebec 24% and British Columbia 14%.

* Prairies: Manitoba, Saskatchewan and Alberta

** Atlantic: Newfoundland, Prince Edward Island, Nova Scotia and New Brunswick

Figure 3. Canadian provinces' share of scientific production in MHWP, 1991-2002

Source: Compiled by Science-Metrix from the Medline database.

Table 1 reveals that output in MHWP is rising steadily in Ontario and in British Columbia. Quebec, Alberta and the smaller provinces are experiencing more erratic patterns. However, the number of papers is quite small at the provincial level, and one should be careful in the interpretation of these statistics.

Table 1. Number of papers in MHWP research by Canadian province, 1991-2002

Province	1991-1993	1994-1996	1997-1999	2000-2002	TOTAL
Ontario	26	31	55	65	177
Quebec	14	13	27	26	80
British Columbia	4	6	11	15	36
Alberta	9	4	6	15	34
Nova Scotia	3	3	7	7	20
Manitoba	4	8	4	3	19
Saskatchewan	1	3	2	4	10
New Brunswick		1		1	2
Newfoundland	1			1	2
Prince Edward Island			1		1
Canada TOTAL	62	69	113	137	381

Source: Compiled by Science-Metrix from the Medline database.

Figure 4 shows that Manitoba, although not a large producer overall, is the leader in terms of papers per capita. It also confirms the leadership position exerted by Ontario and shows that Alberta is also an important producer of scientific output in MHWP research considering its size. On the other hand, British Columbia is below the Canadian average output per capita. Nova Scotia, which appears as part of the Atlantic Provinces, also scores highly in terms of papers per capita.

Figure 4. Papers per million inhabitants per province, 1991-2002

Source: Compiled by Science-Metrix from the Medline database.

Figure 5 shows that, although the Atlantic Provinces' overall output is low, it is nonetheless more important than that observed generally in biomedical science – in other words, these provinces specialize in MHWP. In Table 1, it is immediately clear that Nova Scotia is the province that pulls the Atlantic in terms of specialization. Manitoba comes second after these provinces, thus confirming that in relative terms Manitoba is one of the leaders in Canada in MHWP. Ontario is also specialized in this field, which confirms that Ontario is the clear leader in MHWP in Canada in absolute terms, and its position as leader is confirmed by two relative measures (i.e., papers per capita and index of specialization). Saskatchewan, Quebec, British Columbia and Alberta do not specialize in this field.

It is important to note that since research on MHWP appears to be nascent in Canada, these readings might be subject to change in the near future, not only in terms of papers per capita but also in terms of specialization index.

Figure 5. Specialization index of Canadian provinces, 1991-2002.

Source: Compiled by Science-Metrix from the Medline database.

4. Scientific output at the urban and institutional levels

Table 2 shows that, at the urban level, Toronto is the clear leader overall in terms of MHWP. One can also see here that its output is rising steadily. Montreal occupies the second rank, while Vancouver comes third. London and Hamilton complete this ranking of Canadian cities, with at least two papers per year on average. Winnipeg, Edmonton, Quebec City, Ottawa and Halifax all have at least one paper on MHWP per year on average. Halifax is the only city from the Atlantic region that makes it to the ranks of Canadian cities, having published at least 6 papers during the 1991-2002 period.

Table 2. Most productive Canadian cities in MHWP research, 1991-2002*

City	1991-1993	1994-1996	1997-1999	2000-2002	TOTAL
Toronto	11	16	19	33	79
Montreal	11	8	18	18	55
Vancouver	4	4	10	12	30
London	4	3	11	10	28
Hamilton	3	5	9	9	26
Winnipeg	4	8	4	3	19
Edmonton	7	2	3	7	19
Quebec	1	5	7	6	19
Ottawa	3	1	5	7	16
Halifax	3	2	2	6	13
Calgary	1	1	1	7	10
Kingston	2	1	3	3	9
Saskatoon	1	1	2	2	6
Wolfville		1	4	1	6

* Cities that produced a minimum of 6 papers over the period (1991-2002)

Source: Compiled by Science-Metrix from the Medline database.

There is no institution in Canada that really stands out as a very large producer of papers on MHWP. In fact, the leader, McMaster University, has only two papers per year on average in the field. Other leaders include the Université de Montréal, University of Toronto, University of British Columbia and University of Western Ontario – all with at least 1.5 papers per year on average. Although Manitoba stands out at the provincial level in terms of its size, the University of Manitoba only managed to publish one paper on MHWP per year on average.

Table 3. Most productive Canadian institutions in MHWP research, 1991-2002*

Institution	1991-1993	1994-1996	1997-1999	2000-2002	TOTAL
McMaster University	2	4	9	9	24
Université de Montréal	2	6	3	10	21
University of Toronto	3	6	2	10	21
University of British Columbia	2	3	7	7	19
University of Western Ontario	4	2	5	7	18
Centre for Addiction and Mental Health	6	2	5	4	17
Université Laval		5	7	4	16
University of Alberta	6	1	3	5	15
York University	2	3	2	7	14
University of Manitoba	2	6	1	3	12
UQÀM	3	1	6	2	12
McGill University	5		2	2	9
Dalhousie University	3	1	1	3	8
Queen's University	1	1	3	3	8
University of Calgary	1	1	1	5	8
Acadia University		1	4	1	6
Institute for Work & Health			1	5	6
University Health Network			3	3	6

* Institutions that produced a minimum of 6 papers over the period (1991-2002)

Source: Compiled by Science-Metrix from the Medline database.

5. Scientific output at the researcher level

Table 4 comprises researchers with at least three papers in the field of MHWP. These data were validated manually to detect erroneous homonymic counts¹ and to determine the authors' affiliations. Annex 2 presents all the authors who produced at least one paper on MHWP between 1991 and 2002 with a Canadian as first author and that were indexed in Medline.

McMaster University is confirmed as the leading centre on MHWP research in Canada, since in addition to having the greatest number of papers per institution, it has the largest number of authors in the list of most active researchers in the field (seven authors). The Centre for Addiction and Mental Health (CAMH) and Université Laval, which respectively ranked sixth and seventh in terms of the most active institutions in MHWP, both rank second in terms of number of most active researchers (with four researchers each). The Institute for Work & Health and UQÀM have three top-ranking researchers each, while Acadia University, Université de Montréal, University of Toronto and York University have two researchers each.

Although the majority of the most active researchers are located in universities, there are also researchers from the CAMH (as seen above), from the Centre hospitalier affilié universitaire de Québec (CHA Québec), from the Douglas Hospital in Montreal, from Health Canada and from the Institute for Work & Health – thus, about a quarter of leading researchers are located outside a university (that is not to say that these centres are unaffiliated to a university though).

¹ For instance, Smith, J. could actually be two authors, e.g. Jennifer Smith or John Smith. Of course, it would be an error to impute 10 papers to a J. Smith if Jennifer had written 6 papers and John 4. The validation involves checking papers one by one to ascertain that counts by author are due to a single researcher rather than homonyms.

Table 4. Most productive Canadian researchers in MHWP research, 1991-2002*

Name	Institution	Unit
Asmundson, Gord	University of Regina	Faculty of Kinesiology and Health Studies
Beiser, Morton	CAMH	Social, Prevention and Health Policy Research Dept.
Berkowitz, Jonathan	University of British Columbia	Department of Family Practice
Bourbonnais, Renée	Université Laval	Département de réadaptation
Boyer, Richard	Université de Montréal	Centre de recherche Fernand-Seguin
Brisson, Chantal	Université Laval	Département de médecine sociale et préventive
Brunet, Alain	Douglas Hospital	Department of Psychiatry
Burke, Ronald J.	York University	Schulich School of Business
Chappell, Neena L.	University of Victoria	Centre on Aging
Cherry, Nicola	University of Alberta	Department of Public Health Sciences
Cole, Donald C.	Institute for Work & Health	Unknown
Cunningham, Charles	McMaster University	Dept. of Psychiatry & Behavioural Neurosciences
Dewa, Carolyn	CAMH	Social Prevention and Health Policy Research Dept.
Duquette, André	Université de Montréal	Faculte des sciences infirmieres
Eyles, John	McMaster University	Department of Clinical Epidemiology & Biostatistics
Glancy, Graham D.	McMaster University	Department of Psychiatry
Goering, Paula	CAMH	Social Prevention and Health Policy Research Dept.
Gottlieb, B. H.	University of Guelph	Department of Psychology
Greenglass, Esther	York University	Department of Psychology
Harvie, Phyllis	Acadia University	Psychology Department
Ibrahim, Selahadin	Toronto	Institute for Work & Health
Kelloway, E. Kevin	Saint Mary's University	Department of Management
Larocque, Brigitte	CHUQ	Unité de recherche en santé des populations
Laschinger, Heather K.	University of Western Ontario	School of Nursing
Leiter, Michael	Acadia University	Psychology Department
Lendrum, Bonnie	McMaster University	School of Nursing
McDonough, Peggy	University of Toronto	Department of Public Health Sciences
Mergler, Donna	UQÀM	Department des sciences biologiques - CINBIOSE
Messing, Karen	UQÀM	Department des sciences biologiques - CINBIOSE
Mishara, Brian Leslie	UQÀM	CRISE
Moisan, Jocelyne	Université Laval	Groupe de Recherche en Epidemiologie
Mustard, Cam	Institute for Work & Health	Unknown
Norton, Ron	University of Winnipeg	Department of Psychology
Patten, Scott B.	University of Calgary	Department of Psychiatry
Regehr, Cheryl	University of Toronto	School of Social Work
Shamian, Judith	Health Canada	Nursing Policy Office
Shannon, Harry	McMaster University	Department of Clinical Epidemiology & Biostatistics
Smart, Reginald G.	CAMH	Addiction Research Foundation Division
Stewart, N.J.	University of Saskatchewan	College of Nursing
Vézina, Michel	Université Laval	Département de médecine sociale et préventive
Walters, Vivienne	McMaster University	Department of Sociology
Woodward, Christel	McMaster University	Community Care Research Centre

* Researchers with at least three papers during the 1991-2002 period.

Source: Compiled by Science-Metrix from the Medline database.

6. Conclusion

The field of mental health in the workplace (MHWP) is a nascent scientific undertaking. Although MHWP's economic importance is well established, only about one-fifth of a percent of biomedical papers address this issue. Despite this, the field is growing in absolute terms at the world level, that is, from 535 papers indexed in Medline in 1991 to 940 in 2002 – a growth of 75% in 12 years.

Although overall output is still low, research on MHWP is growing faster in Canada than at the world level. During the last three years, the number of papers by Canada has tripled, and they now account for 5.5% of the world output in the field. Canada specializes in this field, having a proportion of papers on MHWP that is 20% higher than that of papers in Medline during the 1991-2002 period.

Within Canada, Ontario is the clear overall leader. It produces 46% of Canadian output and ranks second in papers per capita and third in terms of specialization in the field. Although Nova Scotia and Manitoba are not strong contenders in absolute terms, they rank highly in papers per capita as well as in terms of specialization in the field.

The cities that are most active in the field are Toronto and Montreal, while Vancouver, London and Hamilton are cities with at least two papers on MHWP per year on average. Not surprisingly, leading institutions in the field – McMaster University, Université de Montréal, University of Toronto, University of British Columbia and University of Western Ontario - are located in these cities.

Three-quarters of the top twenty researchers in the field are from universities. McMaster and Laval provide the largest number of leaders (four researchers each), while York hosts two of the leading researchers in the field.

The statistics presented in this report show that scientific activity in the field is still low. As such, the law of large numbers may not apply yet, and one should expect to see some volatility in the ranks of leading entities - be they provinces, cities, institutions and researchers - in the coming years. As such, this report provides an indication of research at an early stage in the development of the field, and one could expect changes in the geographical distribution of activities as the field matures in the next decade.

Annex 1. Number of MHWP papers by province and by city, 1991-2002

Province	City	1991-1993	1994-1996	1997-1999	2000-2002	TOTAL
Ontario						177
	Toronto	11	16	19	33	79
	London	4	3	11	10	28
	Hamilton	3	5	9	9	26
	Ottawa	3	1	5	7	16
	Kingston	2	1	3	3	9
	Guelph	1	1	3		5
	Sudbury	1	1	2	1	5
	Windsor			1	2	3
	St. Catharines		2			2
	Waterloo			2		2
	Brockville	1				1
	Collingwood		1			1
Quebec						80
	Montreal	11	8	18	18	55
	Quebec	1	5	7	6	19
	Rimouski	1				1
	Sherbrooke	1		1	2	4
	Trois-Rivières			1		1
British Columbia						36
	Vancouver	4	4	10	11	30
	Victoria		2		1	3
	Prince George				2	2
	Salmon Arm			1		1
Alberta						34
	Edmonton	7	2	3	7	19
	Calgary	1	1	1	7	10
	Lethbridge	1	1	1		3
	Red Deer			1		1
	Fort McMurray				1	1
Nova Scotia						20
	Halifax	3	2	1	6	13
	Wolfville		1	4	1	6
	Sydney			1		1
Manitoba						19
	Winnipeg	4	8	4	3	19
Saskatchewan						10
	Saskatoon	1	1	2	2	6
	Regina		2		2	4
New Brunswick						2
	Moncton		1			1
	Saint John				1	1
Newfoundland						2
	St. John's	1			1	2
Prince Edward Island						1
	Charlottetown			1		1
TOTAL	Canada	62	69	113	137	381

Source: Compiled by Science-Metrix from the Medline database.

Annex 2. Researchers who published at least one paper on MHWP with a Canadian as first author, 1991-2002

Abenheim, L	Beaton, R	Braun, K	Christenson, J M
Abrams, Karen M	Beaudet, M P	Bremner, R	Clarke, D
Acorn, S	Beaudry, J	Bricault, N	Clements, Paul T
Adlaf, E M	Beaumont, L	Brillon, P	Clifford, Tammy J
Adler, S	Bedard, D	Brisson, R J	Cockerill, Rhonda
Adrian, M	Begin, S	Brisson, C	Cohen, C
Agro, K	Beiser, M	Brisson, J	Colantonio, A
Alary, M	Beland, Francois	Brodeur, J	Cole, D C
Ali, J	Belanger, B	Brophy, J T	Collins, E
Allard, P	Belanger, S	Brotheridge, Celeste M	Collins, P I
Allen, C	Bell, C E	Brown, G T	Colotla, V A
Allerdings, M D	Bellavance, F	Brown, J	Comeau, M
Alleyne, B C	Benard, J	Brown, J B	Conlon, M
Allison, D G	Bergeron, R	Brown, K D	Connaughty, S
Almost, J	Berkowitz, J	Brown-DeGagne, A M	Connelly, I
Alvarado, Beatriz E	Best, J A	Browne, G	Cook, J V
Andermann, F	Bhaskara, S M	Bruce, Shirliana	Cook, K
Antony, M M	Bienefeld, M	Brunet, A	Copes, R
Arklie, M	Binkley, K E	Bryant, H E	Corbin, S
Armstron-Esther, C A	Birch, Stephen	Buckley, Richard E	Cormier, N
Armstrong, B	Blackford, K A	Bullock, L	Corneil, W
Armstrong-Stassen, M	Blackhouse, G	Burke, R J	Cossette, S
Arsenault, A	Blair, Nancy	Bury, Alison S	Coupland, N J
Ashforth, B E	Blake, J	Byrne, C	Couture, R T
Asmundson, G J	Blanchard, R	Cadsky, O	Coutu-Wakulczyk, G M
Aston, J	Blanchette, C	Calvert, B L	Craven, M A
Aubin, Ginette	Block, L	Camfield, C	Crockett, D J
Aubin, M	Bobocel, D R	Camfield, P	Crowe, J
Auger, C	Boivin, Diane B	Campbell, M Karen	Crustolo, A M
Averill, Jennifer B	Bonin, M F	Cann, B	Culp, D
Avison, W R	Boon, L	Cantin, B	Cunningham, C E
Avotri, J Y	Boucher, C	Cargo, M	Cunningham, D A
Baba, V V	Boudreau, R A	Carlson, D	Dab, W
Bagby, R Michael	Bourassa, D C	Carlson, P	Dagenais, G R
Bailey, P A	Bourassa, M	Caron, Staci	Daigle, M S
Bailey, P H	Bourbonnais, R	Carron, A V	Daines, P A
Bairati, I	Bourdouxhe, M A	Casey, A	D'Arcy, Carl
Baker, B	Bourgault, C	Centerwall, A R	David, M
Bakker, D	Bourgine, M	Chalifour, J	Davidson, S
Baldwin, M	Boustead, R	Chambers, L W	Davies, B
Bardon, E	Bouthillette, F	Chan-Yeung, M	Davies, Sharon
Barham, L	Boutilier, M A	Chappell, N L	Davis, J R
Baril, R H	Bowen, P	Charpentier, Nicole	Day, A L
Barling, J	Bowman, M L	Chartrand, E	Day, M
Barnes, G E	Boyer, G	Chehaitly, A	de Bosset, F
Barrette, Jacques	Boyer, R	Chen, S	de Man, A F
Basinski, A	Boyle, M	Cherry, N M	Dean, R A
Baylard, J F	Bradford, J	Chilcott, L A	Deaudelin, C
Bean, G	Brandon, R A	Choudhry, U	Del Ser, Teodoro
Beaton, D	Brands, B	Choy, T	Delmas, Philippe

DeLuca, V M	FitzGibbon, G M	Gregoire, M	Ibrahim, S A
Demers, P A	Fleetham, J A	Gregor, F	Iezzi, A
Denney, D	Flemons, W W	Gregory, D	Infante-Rivard, C
Dennis, R	Ford, J S	Grenier, J L	Irvine, J
Denton, Margaret	Fortier, I	Griffith, L	Irvine, M J
Dewa, C S	Fortin, M	Grunfeld, E	Isaacs, S
Dion, G	Foster, S	Grypma, S	Isbister, W
Dolan, S L	Foucault, C	Grzybowski, S	Iverson, G L
Donald, J	Fournier, Marc A	Guertin, S C	Iwasaki, Y
Dooley, J	Fraboni, M	Guidotti, T L	Jackson, D N
Doran, Diane	Frankel, S	Guilleminault, C	Jackson, T
Dow-Clarke, R Anne	Fraser, K L	Guruge, S	Jacobson, S J
Dowin, S	Freeman, S J	Guyatt, G	Jacono, B J
Downie, F	French, S	Haase, Mary	Jacono, J J
Drolet, D	Frizzell, C	Hachey, R	Jamal, M
Ducharme, F	Frombach, I K	Hafer, C	James, Francine O
Duchscher, J E	Frost, P	Hagey, R	Jewers, R
Dugbartey, A T	Fry, P S	Hall, B	Johnson, C
Dumais, L	Gafni, Amiram	Hall, W	Johnson, P J
Dumais, W	Gagnon, M	Haney, Colleen J	Johnson, R L
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Duquette, A	Gaskowski, P	Harrick, L	Jones, M W
Durand, Marie-Jose	Gauthier, R	Harris, A	Jones, N
Dussault, M	Geddes, J	Harrison, Margaret J	Joyce, Anthony S
Dyck, Dianne	Gerber, G J	Harrisson, Madelaine	Jreige, Steve
Dyck, Isabel	Gerlach, Jacquelyn	Harvie, P	Julien, D
Eaves, D	Lochhaas	Harwood, G	Juniper, E F
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Escalona, E	Gillrie, C	Hepburn, C G	Katz, J
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Fargas-Babjak, A	Goering, P	Hilditch, J R	Kerouac, S
Farrar, S	Gold, N	Hill, J	Kerr, K L
Feather, J	Goldberg, G	Hodgetts, G	Kerr, M
Feeny, D	Gordon, K	Hodgins, D C	King, A
Feinstein, Anthony	Gorodzinsky, Fabian	Holness, D L	King, W D
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Finestone, H M	Green, P	Hughes, D	Knoop, R
Fischer, B	Greenglass, E R	Hylton, J H	Knott, Theresa
Fitch, M	Gregg, Robin	Iacono, W G	Koch, W J

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Konarski, R	Lin, E	McKelvie, R	Nilsson, T
Kositsky, A J	Lippel, K	McKessock, D	Nisker, J A
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Krahn, Harvey	Livingstone, H A	McLeod, R B	Noh, S
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Kuch, K	Loisel, Patrick	McRae, M P	Norton, G R
Kumar, S	Loiselle, Carmen G	Mead, Shery	Norton, P G
Kunz, J L	Loiselle, J	Medved, W	Norton, P J
Kushner, Kaysi Eastlick	Loney, P	Mercier, C	Novak, M
Labreche, F P	Loo, R	Mergler, D	Nutt, D J
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Leach, P	Marriott, A	Montesanto, B	Ozanne, W G
LeBlanc, Manon Mireille	Martin, G L	Moore, C F	Pace, A
Leclaire, R	Maslach, C	Moore, L	Packer, D
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Lee, Raymond T	Massicotte, P R	Morrison, H I	Palla, Linda L O'Brien
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Lees, R E	May, K A	Moskowitz, D S	Paterson, D H
Legault, E	Mayr, J	Moszczynski, Alice B	Paterson, Michael
Leigh, G	Mayville, K	Mueser, Kim T	Patrick, L
Leiter, M P	McAfee, J G	Mulder, J	Patten, S B
Lemay, F	McAiney, C A	Murnaghan, M Lucas	Patton, D
Lemieux, A P	McCain, G A	Murphy, S	Paul, J
Lendrum, B	McCall, M	Murray, M	Peat, J K
Lenton, R	McCallum, M	Murray, Michael	Perrault, G
Lepage, D	McColl, Mary Ann	Murray, R P	Perusse, M
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Levy, M	McDonough, Peggy	Myrick, Florence	Pettigrew, F P
Lewis, J	McDowell, I	Nanson, J	Philibert, L
Leznoff, A	McIndoe, K I	Nelson, T M	Phipps, L
Lian, Jason	McIntosh, J	Newbold, B	Pickett, W
Liao, J	McIntyre, J W	Nicholson, I R	Pike, K

Piper, W E	Sale, Joanna E M	Stoddart, Greg	Vinje, G
Plotkin, D	Salmi, L R	Stratford, P	Vyskocil, A
Polatajko, H J	Sandhu, B K	Streiner, D	Wakeling, H
Polimeni-Walker, I	Sanford, M	Stringer, B	Wall, R
Pongruengphant, R	Sassine, M P	Strohschein, Lisa	Wald, R
Potokar, J P	Saulnier, P	Stuart, P	Walsh, G
Pranger, T	Saurel-Cubizolles, M J	Stutzer, C	Walsh, G W
Priest, R G	Savard, J	Suedfeld, P	Walters, V
Proulx, R	Sawka, E	Suissa, S	Wang, J
Provencher, Helene L	Schechter, J	Sullivan, T	Waridel, S
Queinnec, Y	Schell, B H	Swenson, J R	Waters, B G
Raboud, J M	Schemitsch, E H	Sylvestre, M	Watson, David C
Rae, S	Schlosar, H	Szalai, J P	Watson, J
Ratner, P A	Schmidt, G	Tanguay, S M	Watterson, A
Rebeiro, K L	Scholten, D	Tardif, R	Way, M
Rector, N A	Schopler, E	Tate, R	Weber, W
Regehr, C	Scott, F E	Taylor, A W	Weiss, D S
Regehr, G	Seguin, R	Taylor, S	Wells, S
Rehm, J	Seifert, A M	Teasell, R W	Whelan, T J
Rehm, J	Semchuk, Karen M	Teschke, K	Wiebe, J
Reid, Doreen	Semenic, Sonia E	Tett, R P	Wiele, K
Reilly, S M	Sewitch, M J	Thommasen, H V	Wild, T C
Reutter, L I	Sexton, L	Thomson, Donna	Wilk, P
Rexroth, D	Shain, M	Thurston, N E	Wilkins, K
Rhodes, A	Shamian, J	Tien, G	Willan, A R
Richard, L	Shannon, H S	Tipliski, V M	Williams, K
Richardsen, A M	Shapiro, C M	Tobe, S W	Williams, R
Richardson, J S	Shaw, Brenda Laurie	Torrance, G	Williams-Keeler, L
Rivard, G E	Sheehy, O	Towers, A M	Willmer, J
Roach, Sally M	Shercliffe, R J	Townsend, E A	Wilson, K G
Roberts, J	Shields, M	Trojan, Lorraine	Wishart, L
Robichaud, L	Shrier, Ian	Trott, M	Wong, C
Robinson, Gail Erlick	Shulman, K I	Truchon, G	Woodcox, V
Robinson, S	Sibbald, W J	Trudel, M	Wood-Dauphinee, S
Robson, L	Sidani, Souraya	Tsai, W	Woodward, C A
Rodgers, C D	Sinclair, D E	Tully, S	Woolfenden, S R
Roesch, R	Singer, J	Turner, R J	Wowk, A
Rogers, H L	Single, E	Turritin, J	Wu, Z
Rogers, J M	Skelton-Green, J	Tyson, P D	Xie, X
Rogers, K A	Smart, R G	Tziner, A	Yonge, Olive
Roithmayr, Tony	Smith, B	Underwood, J	Yoo, D
Rondeau, K V	Smith, C A	Vachon, M L	Young, A
Rook, M	Smith, D	Van Ameringen, M R	Zacharatos, A
Rosenbloom, D	Smylie, J A	van der Wal, R	Zaza, C
Rosie, John S	Spaulding, S J	van Netten, C	Zeitlin, S B
Ross, H E	Speechley, Kathy N	Vedantham, K	Zeytinoglu, Isik Urla
Rossignol, M	Speechley, M	Venter, A	Zhang, J
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Rousseau, A	Steel, G D	Vernich, L	Zirul, S
Royer, N	Stephenson, R	Vezina, L	Zitzelsberger, L
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Russell, Grant M	Stewart, J	Vigil, Gloria J	Victoria
Rzasa, T	Stewart, N J	Villeneuve, M	Zuroff, David C
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